

INFLUENCE OF SILICA NANOPARTICLES ON THE CHEMICAL, SURFACE AND MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF PLA AND PCL MIXTURES

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Abstract: *Considering the growing problems related to climate change and environmental pollution, in this research the impact of the addition of silica nanoparticles (SiO₂) on the chemical, surface and morphological properties of mixtures with different proportions of biodegradable polymers were tested. Biodegradable polylactide (PLA) and polycaprolactone (PCL), which could find their purpose in the making of letterpress printing plates, were used. In the mixture, the PLA was a continuous phase, while the PCL was a dispersed phase. Previous research has shown that the addition of silicon dioxide nanoparticles can change the interfacial properties of two polymers, i.e. nanoparticles act as a compatibilizer and contribute to better miscibility of two, otherwise immiscible polymers and thus affect the functional properties of the mixture. The aim of this paper was to examine the influence of SiO₂ nanoparticles on the chemical, surface and morphological properties of a PLA and PCL mixture. FTIR-ATR spectroscopy was performed in order to get insight whether the silica has had an effect on chemical changes within the mixture. Surface free energy was determined from contact angle measurements, and SEM microscopy was performed to provide insight into the morphology of the samples itself.*

Keywords: biodegradable polymers, polylactide, polycaprolactone, silica nanoparticles

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to rising awareness of climate change and pollution, there has been an increase in the use of biodegradable materials. In order to make their use as widespread as possible, it is necessary to examine their properties and adapt them to the occasion for which they will be used. Biodegradable materials are materials of natural or synthetic origin that, through the action of bacteria, fungi or other microorganisms, enter the biochemical process of converting materials into water, biomass, carbon dioxide or methane in a certain period of time. Biodegradation depends on conditions such as location, temperature, humidity, presence of oxygen and microorganisms, the environment in which it is carried out, on the material itself and its properties. (What is biodegradation?, n.d.); (Leja and Lewandowicz, 2010); (Vukelić, Pavunc Samaržija and Vujasinović, 2017); (Tokiwa, Calabia, Ugwu and Aiba, 2009); (Rudnik, 2008).

Polylactide (PLA) is a biodegradable and bioactive thermoplastic aliphatic polyester. At room temperature it is brittle, regardless of the degree of crystallinity. It is obtained from corn starch, sugar cane and tapioca. Pure PLA has a glass transition temperature (T_g) between 50 and 60 °C and a melting point (T_m) at a temperature of about 180 °C. Above the glass PLA is in a rubbery or viscoelastic state, and below in a glassy state. In order to expand its field of application, it has been shown that mixing with various flexible polymers can favorably affect its mechanical properties. Studies have shown that in a mixture with PCL (polycaprolactone), materials with a wide range of physical properties and biodegradability are formed. Its biodegradation time is about 6 months. Its mechanical properties are similar to those of polyethylene terephthalate, so it can serve as a substitute for it. The advantage of using PLA is that it is obtained from renewable sources, and in addition, it is biodegradable, compostable, and can be recycled. On the other hand, PLA has some limitations such as low toughness which makes it a very brittle material, then a long time of degradation which can be a problem when products made of PLA after use improperly dispose of and hydrophobicity and inertness. Under the simulated landfill conditions, 90% of the PLA biodegrade in ninety days (Ebnesajjad, 2013); (Armentano et al., 2015); (Madhavan Nampoothiri, Nair and John, 2010); (Rasal, Janorkar and Hirt, 2010); (Boonmee, Kositanont and Leejarkpai, 2016). PCL is a synthetic aliphatic polyester that is produced from crude oil and is completely biodegradable. It is a hydrophobic, semi-

crystalline polymer with a melting point of about 60 °C and a glass transition temperature of about -60 °C. High molecular weight PCL has properties similar to polyethylene. It can be added to PLA, but also to other brittle polymers to increase their resistance to breakage. Its degradation time is around 3 years but some studies have shown that PCL can be completely degraded in twelve days with the addition of fungi of the genus *Penicillium*, and with the addition of fungi of the genus *Aspergillus* in just 6 days (Ebnesajjad, 2013), (Woodruff and Hutmacher, 2010), (Nair, Sekhar, Nampoothiri and Pandey, 2017). Fumed silica SiO₂ nanoparticles (Aerosil 200) were added in PLA/PCL mixture in order to define the influence of nanoparticles on the chemical, surface and morphological properties of the mixture.

In this paper the results of the influence of SiO₂ nanoparticles on the chemical, surface and morphological properties of PLA and PCL mixtures were reported.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

2.1 Materials

Materials on which the tests were performed were PLA, PCL and SiO₂ nanoparticles (Aerosil 200). PLA was supplied by Inego™ 3251D, Nature Works LLC, USA. Its mean molecular weight is 55400 daltons, melt flow index is 35 g/10 min (190 °C, 2.16 kg) and 80 g/10 min (210 °C, 2.16 kg). PCL was supplied by Capa 6800, Perstorp, UK. Its mean molecular weight is 80000 daltons and melt flow index is 3 g/10 min (160 °C, 2.16 kg). Aerosil 200 is a hydrophilic fumed silica with a specific surface area of 200 m²/g. Its content based on ignited material is >99.8%. SiO₂ have the function of a compatibilizer, i.e. to improve the miscibility of two otherwise immiscible polymers. Samples were mixed in the Brabender kneader (C. W. Brabender Instruments, Inc., USA). The mass of the samples was around 40 grams as this corresponded to the capacity that the kneader could receive. The samples were placed in the kneader at a temperature of 190 °C because that temperature can completely melt the PLA. Kneader's speed is 60 rounds per minute. The samples were mixed for 5 minutes and after that, they were cut into small pieces so they could be pressed and cut into 10 x 10 x 0.14 cm tiles. The pressing was also done at a temperature of 190 °C and a pressure of 16 MPa. The pressing lasted for a total of 11 minutes. After cooling down, the obtained samples were ready for further testing. The list of the samples is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of the samples

Sample name	$m(\text{PLA}) / \text{g}$	$m(\text{PCL}) / \text{g}$	$m(\text{SiO}_2) / \text{g}$
PLA/PCL 50/50	20	20	0
PLA/PCL 70/30	28	12	0
PLA/PCL 90/10	36	4	0
PLA/PCL 50/50 + 3% SiO ₂	20	20	1.2
PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% SiO ₂	28	12	1.2
PLA/PCL 90/10 + 3% SiO ₂	36	4	1.2

2. 2 Measurement methods

The tests performed on the samples were FTIR-ATR spectroscopy, contact angle measurement, surface free energy calculation and cross-section SEM analysis. FTIR analysis was performed using a Shimadzu IRAffinity-1 FTIR Spectrophotometer, Japan. Resolution of the scans was 4 cm^{-1} and a total of 15 scans were taken for each sample. From the obtained samples, it was checked whether any chemical changes had occurred within the mixtures and whether the addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles affected the chemical changes in the mixtures. In order to determine the surface free energy of the samples, it was first necessary to obtain contact angles for the three reference liquids: water, diiodomethane, and glycerol. The contact angles were measured using Data Physics OCA 30 goniometer by the Sessile drop method so that 10 drops of each liquid were applied to the samples at different places on the surface. The droplet volume was $1 \mu\text{m}^3$. Then, the mean value of the contact angle for each of the three liquids was calculated, and using these results and the surface free energies of the reference liquids (Table 2), the surface free energies of the samples were determined by the OWRK method.

Table 2: Surface free energies of reference liquids

Liquids	$\gamma^D (\text{mJ/m}^2)$	$\gamma^P (\text{mJ/m}^2)$	$\gamma_L (\text{mJ/m}^2)$
Redistilled water (Störm et al.) $\sigma = 2,0 \mu\text{S/cm}$	21.80	51.00	72.80
Glycerol (Van Oss et al.) 99,5% of purity	34.00	30.00	64.00
Diiodomethane (Störm et al.) 99,0% of purity	50.80	0.00	50.80

For SEM analysis, it was necessary to cut the samples into small pieces after which they first had to be evaporated with gold ions for a better quality of the results. Images of the samples were taken at 300× and 1000× magnifications. JEOL JSM-6060LV scanning electron microscope was used in this paper.

3 RESULTS

3.1 FTIR-ATR spectroscopy

FTIR specters and specific band values of the samples are shown in Figure 1. Red arrows represent PLA bands and black arrows represent PCL bands. CH stretching appears at 2943 and 2864 cm^{-1} for PCL in all samples except PLA/PCL 90/10 and PLA/PCL 90/10 + 3% of SiO_2 . CH stretching specific to PLA appears only in the sample PLA/PCL 90/10 + 3% SiO_2 at 2993 and 2947 cm^{-1} . C=O stretching for PCL is visible at 1720 cm^{-1} and it appears in the sample PLA/PCL 50/50 and PLA/PCL 50/50 + 3% SiO_2 . For the sample PLA/PCL 70/30 there are two C=O peaks, one at 1720 cm^{-1} which belongs to PCL and the other at 1745 which belongs to PLA. In the rest of the samples there is only one C=O peak at 1745 cm^{-1} which belongs to PLA. At 1452 cm^{-1} CH_3 bending of PLA can be found and it appears in all samples. CH deformation specific for PLA is visible at 1363 cm^{-1} and also at 1382 cm^{-1} for the samples PLA/PCL 70/30, PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% of SiO_2 , PLA/PCL 90/10 and PLA/PCL 90/10 + 3% of SiO_2 . The peak at 1268 cm^{-1} represents C=O bend of PLA and it appears in all of the samples. C-O-C stretching of PCL at 1240 is also visible in all samples. C-O stretching appears in PLA at 1180, 1130 and 1082 cm^{-1} and also in PCL at 1294 and 1180 cm^{-1} . The peak at 867 cm^{-1} represents C-COO stretching of PLA and it is visible in all of the samples. No significant change was observed in the samples, so it can be concluded that no chemical changes occurred within the samples (Popa et al., 2017); (Shalumon et al., 2011); (Prajongtat et al., 2019); (Chong, Lim and Sultana, 2015); (Gómez-Lizárraga et al., 2017); (Lee et al., 2015); (Kemala, Budianto and Soegiyono, 2012). Also, there were no specific peaks that will represent SiO_2 which may be result of covering specific SiO_2 bands with specific PLA and PCL bands and also due to reduced device sensitivity.

Figure 1: FTIR specters of the samples

3. 2 Contact angles and surface free energy

Figure 2 presents the results of contact angle measurements. It can be seen from the graph that the values of contact angles for water are increased by the addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles on all observed samples. One can see a decrease of those values for glycerol and diiodomethane; except the contact angle of glycerol for sample PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% SiO₂. Increasing the proportion of PLA in the mixtures without SiO₂ leads to the lowering of contact angle values for all of the samples and reference liquids except diidomethane for the sample PLA/PCL 90/10. The higher values of contact angles for water in the samples with the addition of SiO₂ indicate the impact of the SiO₂ on the compatibilization of PLA and PCL which has resulted in higher hydrophobicity. Lower values of contact angles for glycerol and diidomethane in the samples with the addition of SiO₂ are the result of increased dispersive part of surface free energy in those samples (Figure 3.b). From Figure 3.a it can be seen that the surface free energy is increased with the higher share of PLA in the mixtures without the addition of SiO₂. Also, the addition of SiO₂ has increased the surface free energy of the samples. The only exception is sample PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% of SiO₂ which has the lowest surface free energy of all the samples. The sample with the highest value of surface free energy is PLA/PCL 90/10 + 3% of SiO₂.

Figure 2: Contact angles of samples for water, glycerol and diiodomethane

Figure 3: Surface free energy of the samples:
a) total, b) dispersive and polar part

3. 3 SEM analysis

Figure 4 represents a cross-section of the samples. Images were taken at 300× magnification for PLA/PCL 50/50 and PLA/PCL 50/50 + 3% SiO₂, and at 1000× magnification for the rest of the samples. From Figure 4.a and 4.b is visible that PLA and PCL form co-continuous phase. With a larger proportion of PLA in the mixture, PCL transforms to the droplet-like phase inside PLA matrix, also known as the sea-island phase, which is visible in Figures 4.c to 4.f. Sample PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% SiO₂ has smaller PCL droplets than sample PLA/PCL 70/30 which is consequence of the addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles. SiO₂ nanoparticles were not observed due to insufficient imaging resolution. (Molavi, Ghasemi, Messori and Esfandeh, 2019); (Luyt and Gasmi, 2016); (Wu et al., 2011); (Nematollahi, Jalali - Arani and Modarress, 2019).

Figure 4: Cross-section of the samples: a) PLA/PCL 50/50, b) PLA/PCL 50/50 + 3% SiO₂, c) PLA/PCL 70/30, d) PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% SiO₂, e) PLA/PCL 90/10, f) PLA/PCL 90/10 + 3% SiO₂

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper the influence of silica nanoparticles on the chemical, surface and morphological properties of PLA and PCL mixtures was investigated and the following can be concluded:

- From FTIR analysis it is clear that no chemical change has occurred within the mixtures and also there were no specific peaks that will represent SiO₂ nanoparticles which may be result of covering specific SiO₂ bands with specific PLA and PCL bands and also due to reduced device sensitivity;
- contact angle results show the increase in the hydrophobicity of the samples with the addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles which can be a sign of the PLA and PCL compatibilization. The addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles has also increased the dispersive part of surface free energy which results in a lower contact angle for glycerol and diiodomethane for all of the samples, except the sample PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% SiO₂ whose surface free energy is lower than of the same sample without the addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles;
- cross-section images show that PLA/PCL 50/50 and PCL 50/50 + 3% SiO₂ form co-continuous phase, while other samples form sea-island phase, i.e. PCL droplet-like phase inside PLA matrix. PLA/PCL 70/30 + 3% SiO₂ forms smaller PCL droplets than the same sample without the

addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles. SiO₂ nanoparticles were not observed due to low imaging resolution.

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